

Management of an Immature Necrotic Mandibular First Molar Using Regenerative Endodontic Procedure With Minor Modification: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Management of necrotic immature teeth is considered a high challenge In endodontics. Among treatment options in such cases is regenerative endodontic procedure. This type of treatment allows root formation by increasing root length, width or both. This case report describes management of an immature permanent molar tooth using regenerative endodontic protocol with minor modification, which yielded in great result after two years follow up.

Case description:

A regenerative endodontic procedure with some modification was performed for an immature necrotic mandibular molar in an 8-year old Saudi boy. At the first appointment, thorough disinfection using antimicrobial agent followed by application of calcium hydroxide to the coronal half of all canals. One week later, the canals were medicated with triple antibiotic (Ciprofloxacin, Metronidazole and Minocycline) for three weeks. Bleeding induction was accomplished in the distal canal and some of the blood was transferred to mesial canals. MTA was placed over canal orifices and the tooth restored by composite and stainless steel crown. The patient was recalled at (3, 6, 12 and 24) months for evaluation. The patient was asymptomatic, there was complete periapical healing and apical closure, in addition to an increase in root length and wall thickness at 24 months follow up.

Conclusion:

Regenerative endodontic procedure for multi rooted immature necrotic teeth can be consider a superior and more valuable treatment option than apexification.

Keywords:

Regenerative Endodontic Procedures, Necrotic tooth, Open apex, Calcium Hydroxide, Triple Antibiotic Paste, MTA.

Pre-operative

26-months

References:

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Good Periodontal Health Equals to Good General Health

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Abstract:

Like many areas of the body, your mouth is teeming with bacteria — most of them harmless. Normally the body's natural defenses and good oral health care, such as daily brushing and flossing, can keep these bacteria under control. However, without proper oral hygiene, bacteria can reach levels that might lead to oral infections, such as tooth decay and gum disease.

In addition, certain medications — such as decongestants, antihistamines, painkillers, diuretics and antidepressants — can reduce saliva flow. Saliva washes away food and neutralizes acids produced by bacteria in the mouth, helping to protect you from microbial invasion or overgrowth that might lead to disease.

Studies also suggest that oral bacteria and the inflammation associated with periodontitis — a severe form of gum disease — might play a role in some diseases. In addition, certain diseases, such as diabetes and HIV/AIDS, can lower the body's resistance to infection, making oral health problems more severe.

Immediate Implant Placement In The Esthetic Zone: Socket Shield Technique Versus Empty Socket Technique For Preservation Of Labial Alveolar Bone Integrity

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Abstract:

Objective: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the clinical and radiographic outcomes of socket shield technique compared with conventional immediate implant placement.

Patients and Methods: Patients with remaining roots in the esthetic zone with intact periodontal condition indicated for extraction were randomly allocated to one of two study arms with 1:1 allocation ratio by using computerized sequence generation: the 'intervention' group whom we placed implant with socket shield technique or the control group whom we placed implant by conventional immediate implant technique

Results: The maximum period of treatment will be fixed at nine months. The patient will be examined preoperative and immediate postoperative then nine months during the study period.

Conclusion: From our point of view Socket shield technique (SST) was considered as one of successful techniques in preservation of alveolar bone integrity specially in terms of minimal or no alveolar bone loss which is recommended specially in the esthetic zone

Keywords:

Implant Placement - The Esthetic Zone

Expeditious Planning Of Dental Implants In Atrophic Jaw

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Abstract:

Tooth loss is very common problem in all age groups, specially in old age; therefore, the use of dental implants is also a common practice. As the age increase, the resorption of alveolar bone also increase. Its difficult to plan dental implant placement in severely resorbed jaw. If we want to place implants in severely resorbed jaws we need to graft the sites and wait for the bone formation and then place implant. Almost it will take 6 month to an year. And extra surgical procedures are needed for grafting. In order to avoid grafting and other surgical procedures we can plan severely resorbed jaw by placing implants in floor of the nose, naso maxillary buttress, zygomatic bone and pterygoid bone in maxilla and in mandible we can engage base of the mandible in anterior mandible, and nerve bypassing in posterior mandible. as the implants have bicortical anchorage we can do immediate loading also. this is not possible in grafted bone.

Keywords:

Atrophic Jaw, Zygomatic Implant, Ptery-goid Implant, Nerve Bypass, Bicortical Implant, Dental Implants, Resorbed Jaw, Alveolar Bone

Figure 1: Figure illustrating implants in nasomaxillary buttress, nasal floor, zygomatic bone and pterygoid bone

References:

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Implant Site: Preparation and Restoration

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Abstract:

Introduction of dental implants and next the implant supported prosthesis has hugely enhanced the quality of life for those partially or fully edentulous patients. Implants provided advantages such as preservation of bone, occlusal vertical dimensions, facial esthetics, improved phonetics, enhancement or granting for restoring of oral proprioception, stability and retention of prosthesis, psychological health and eliminating the need to change. Based on clinical observations it has been suggested that the main issue, the primary interest in current clinical and animal research is the study of dimensional tissue changes that occur following tooth loss and the proper timing for implant placement and loading. Patient desire for improved masticatory function is often given as a primary reason for treatment with implant supported or retained dentures. Implant supported or retained prosthesis have been increasingly accepted as an alternative to conventional dentures for oral rehabilitation of fully or partially edentulous patients. There is a positive relationship between proper dental implant site preparation and highly remarkable implant success rates and patient satisfaction. The selection of a specific prosthetic design for implant supported prosthesis is wide and often controversial but then again the restoration is influenced by the type, size, number and orientation of implants that can be planned in relation to anatomical, surgical and prosthetic considerations.

Keywords:

Implant, Esthetics, Implant site development, Implant site preparation, Implant prosthesis, Bone graft, Guided bone regeneration, Im-mediate implant, Impression techniques.

Figure 1: Placement of bone graft in the gap distance and healing abutment collar height 3mm.

Figure 1: 3 months follow up (labial view)

References:

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Complex patient's Diagnosis and Treatment planning An Interdisciplinary Approach

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Abstract:

Esthetic dentistry requires an understanding of necessary principles, and the associated need for cooperation between restorative dentists and other specialists. When dentofacial esthetics are of concern, collaboration with other specialties such as Oral Surgery and orthodontics should be an integral consideration in treatment planning.

Among the factors that are receiving great emphasis among patients and dentists is excess gingival display, also known as “gummy smile”. This condition has several etiological factors, and knowing the basic principles and how to diagnose each one of these factors is vital for treatment planning, and setting predictable expectations.

Keywords:

Esthetics, excessive gingival display, gummy smile, veneers, dentoalveolar extrusion, dental materials, ceramic restorations, dental adhesives and bonding agents.

Figure 1: Initial image pretreatment

Figure 2: Final image after ortho, and Porcelain veneers

References:

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Evaluation of head and cervical spine posture after functional therapy with twin-block appliances: a randomized controlled trial

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Abstract:

Introduction: Class II malocclusion is characterized by the extension of head in relation to the cervical spine. Some studies have suggested that functional therapy may lead to flexion of head and straightening of cervical spine, which may correct the posture of body and jaws.

Aims: To investigate the changes in head and cervical spine posture after functional therapy with Twin Block appliance in patients with class II – division 1 malocclusion.

Materials and Methods: 48 patients (24 males, 24 females) with class II malocclusion (due to retrognathic mandible) aged 9-13 years old were randomly allocated to two groups: treatment group (who were been treated with Twin Block appliance) and control group. Head and cervical spine posture were evaluated by lateral cephalograms taken in natural head position before and after treatment with an interval of 7 months between first and second cephalogram. T-test were applied to identify any differences between treatment group and control group.

Results: There were statistically significant differences in angles ANB and SNB ($P=0.000$), where there was no statistically significant difference in angle SNA ($P=0.099$). Regarding head posture variables there were statistically significant differences in angles SN/OPT and SPP/OPT, but there were no statistically significant differences SN/CVT, SN/VER, SPP/CVT and SPP/VER ($P=0.089, 0.064$). Regarding cervical spine posture variables there were statistically significant differences in angles OPT/VER ($P=0.000$) and EVT/VER ($P=0.000$), but there were no statistically significant difference in angles EVT/CVT and CVT/VER.

Conclusion: There is bend in head posture between (anterior cranial base and maxilla) and upper cervical spine, and there is posterior decline in upper and lower cervical spine in relation to true vertical in treatment group more than control group.

Keywords:

Head posture, cervical spine, Twin Block, randomized controlled trial.

The use of concentrated autologous fibrin in oral implantology. Material fundamentals and technique modifications to achieve easy, affordable and predictable regeneration for the emerging economies

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Abstract:

Bone regeneration is a frequently needed resource in implant dentistry. Predictability is most important and relies on the operator skills, the surgical techniques selected, and the grafting materials placed on the treated area. Most techniques and materials for modern dentistry are developed in first world economies, and therefore are not suitable for practitioners and populations of the emerging economies. Thereby there is a need for modification and adaptation of these in order to provide quality attention to the highest number of world inhabitants. The use of concentrated autologous fibrin is affordable and efficient, and combined with slight technique modifications it becomes a great ally for the daily practice.

Periodontal muscle training can strength the periodontal support Feet your teeth

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Abstract:

Previous research on periodontal structure and function has shown a significant relationship between periodontal tissue and teeth. This study assessed dentist's beliefs about the relative efficacy of the health of periodontal tissue. A total of 505 patients in general practice were asked to respond to a list of 25 obligatory nourishment for a child while going to have the first teeth, for its effectiveness in dealing with patient's periodontal health especially include chewing hard food. They were also asked to select the three most effective nutrition for periodontal tissue. The indices of patient perceived importance of the periodontal health were derived and each compared with actual effectiveness as determined from a sample of 250 patients.

Although the majority of patient's rated 18 of 25 nutrition as being very effective, there was no significant association between patient perceived nourishment effectiveness and actual effectiveness. The implications for patient training are discussed.

This study supported by only me and my supervisor Alla grigorivna demitrova.

Biography:

NIMA SABZCHAMANARA has completed his dental study from National Medical University Kiev Ukraine with Honored Diploma. Has certified with specialisation in Therapeutic Dentistry in 2018, and is Practicing with Microscopic Dentistry in Private dental clinics in Kyiv, Ukraine.

Microscope demystified

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Abstract:

Magnification is the amplification of the real image of an object that allows a better visual acuity for the professionals .It was considered a support applied in the health area ,it's use grew ,gained significance in the dentistry field and promoted the improvement of operative techniques for a safer and more accurate procedure .Benefits of the Dental operating Microscope including improvements in treatment outcome,ergonomics ,documentation and communication are described .The microscope has become a standard part of the Endodontics armamentarium since the 1980s and it's not endo it's a need for every branch of dentistry from diagnosis to treatment planning for high end technology like lasers .The importance of high levels of Magnification for hard tissue and soft tissue Laser dentistry are emphasised and detailed as this discipline ,like Endodontics ,is also largely reliant on non tactile information for clinical success

From a to z: the adhesive path of rehabilitation to veneers

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Abstract:

A clinical approach based on 20 years of experience with adhesive aesthetic procedures. I'll show you the long path you take to get more conservative treatment. between concepts and clinical cases will demonstrate how we can change our philosophy to diagnose and carry out esthetic and predictable treatments. A detailed protocol of all treatment steps will be presented. A clinical view based on science from planning to cementing is fundamental to achieve treatments of aesthetic and functional high level, so we can fully understand how our biomechanical restorations work.

Keywords:

Figure 1: Figure illustrating a crown dental preparation before pre hybridization and impression procedures.

Figure 2: Figure illustrating approach of occlusal records for a full mouth treatment

Figure 3: Figure illustrating a slide with planning concepts.

Figure 4: Figure illustrating a slide with mock up steps.

Figure 5: Figure illustrating a slide with an example of conservative classic veneers dental preparation.

Figure 5: Figure illustrating a slide with dental preparations steps.

Figure 5: Figure illustrating a slide with a thin porcelain veneers.

Figure 5: Figure illustrating a slide with an example for ceramic fragments (contact lens).

Compromised Airway and Atypical Facial Growth in The Adult Patient: A Case Study in the Redirection of Facial Growth

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Abstract:

This case history is an adult patient with a compromised upper airway, soft tissue dysfunction, and atypical facial growth. The nasal deviation and enlarged turbinates resulted in mouth breathing and soft tissue dysfunction. Atypical growth occurs when the biological balance between bone remodeling and positional displacement is disrupted. Following septoplasty and turbinate reduction to reestablish nasal respiration and myofunctional therapy to retrain the muscles, the atypical growth was redirected to normal. The final result was an overall improvement in general health, esthetics, and well-being.

Keywords:

A typical facial growth, deviated septum, adult compromised airway, myofunctional therapy, soft tissue dysfunction, redirection of facial growth.